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AI4DI Artificial Intelligence for Digitizing Industry

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1 Executive summary

The present document is a deliverable of the AI4DI project, which is co-funded by the ECSEL Joint Undertaking under grant agreement No. 826060 and ECSEL JU Member States.

This document is intended to give an overview of the types of dissemination, communication, and outreach activities planned and undertaken during the project lifetime, in order to raise awareness about the project and ensure the uptake of project results. This deliverable is intended to be read together with AI4DI deliverable “D7.6 AI-based industrial use cases deployment plans for digitising industry”, which details the project’s exploitation and deployment plan and the plans for how to introduce the project results in the market.

This deliverable “D7.8 Final plan and report for use and dissemination of the foreground” (Final PUDF) defines the project dissemination, communication and outreach plans and tools to be applied throughout the AI4DI project. This includes, in particular, the following aspects:

- The definition and description of target groups and communication channels
- Tools for dissemination and communication of project results
- Plans for events
- Dissemination and communication activities’ tracking with key performance indicators

The framework, consisting of the legal documents – Project Grant Agreement (PGA), Project Consortium Agreement (PCA), and National Grant Agreement (NGA) – and the draft PUDF, form the basis for using, disseminating, communicating, and outreach activities for the outcomes of the AI4DI project. In case of any conflicts, the rules defined in the legal documents supersede any rules or recommended practices in the PUDF. In particular, the PCA concerns the consortium internal obligations, while the draft PUDF complements the legal documents by a description of the project-wide dissemination and communication processes, rules and tools to be applied throughout the project. Thus, the PUDF served as the reference document collecting project’s dissemination, communication, and outreach elements.

The AI4DI project's Final plan and report for use and dissemination of the foreground was systematically reviewed and updated on the occasion of each consortium meeting in a dedicated timeslot.

2 Publishable summary

See section 1.

3 Non publishable information

This deliverable is classified as Public, hence all information in this document is publishable.

4 Introduction & Scope

4.1 Purpose and target group

AI4DI is a large and complex project aimed at developing and advancing artificial intelligence solutions for digitizing industry. Consortium partners work on enabling of performance, industry and humanity by Artificial Intelligence (AI) for digitising industry is the key to push the AI revolution in Europe and step into the digital age. Existing services providing state of the art machine learning (ML) and artificial intelligence solutions are currently available in the cloud. In this project, partners transfer machine learning and AI from the cloud to the edge in manufacturing, mobility, and robotics. To achieve these targets this consortium connects factories, processes, and devices within digitised industry by utilizing ML and AI for human machine collaboration, change detection, and detection of abnormalities

4.2 Contributions of partners

Explain which partner were involved and their activities in their various sections

TABLE 1: CONTRIBUTIONS

Chapter	Partner	Contribution
All chapters	TERA	Preparation
7.2	OTH-AW	Description of the AI4DI website

4.3 Relation to other activities in the project

This document describes the overall dissemination, communication, and outreach management of the AI4DI project, including all Work Packages and all Supply Chains. In particular, it provides further guidance and tracking of the activities related to WP7 Dissemination, Exploitation and Standardization.

Because this Plan was applied throughout the project duration, it was considered as a 'living document', i.e. it was enhanced or adapted during the project as required.

5 Dissemination methodology and target groups

5.1 Key concepts and objectives

The following definitions of the key terms used in this document originate from the European Commission's Participant Portal¹:

Communication: "Communication on projects is a strategically planned process, which starts at the outset of the action and continues throughout its entire lifetime, aimed at promoting the action and its results. It requires strategic and targeted measures for communicating about (i) the action and (ii) its results to a multitude of audiences, including the media and the public and possibly engaging in a two-way exchange."

The general purpose of communicating about European projects is to promote European collaborative research and innovation².

AI4DI project communication objectives are the following:

- Defining an effective communication strategy and target groups (target audiences)
- Creating the common project's visual identity (brand)
- Deploying partners' communication channels, implementing the communication
- Evaluating the communication

Communication contributed to supporting dissemination, outreach, and exploitation objectives while targeting stakeholders beyond the immediate interest groups, such as the public at large. Dissemination, per its definition, is "the public disclosure of the results by any appropriate means (other than resulting from protecting or exploiting the results), including by scientific publications in any medium." The dissemination of the project outputs to key stakeholders aims at (1) making the knowledge (results) developed through the project available to the widest audience and (2) enhancing project exploitation potential. Throughout the AI4DI project, communication and dissemination work enhanced public's awareness, informed interested stakeholders, and strengthened the exploitation potential of the created products.

5.2 Definition of target audiences

The target audiences for AI4DI communication, dissemination and outreach include industry, regulatory bodies, policy makers, research/academic community, and the wider public. The communication strategy targets all involved, interested, and potential audiences. The consortium also identified potential interested members who could spread the word of AI4DI key messages, increasing and widening audience participation.

The target audiences for AI4DI can be segmented according to the following criteria, including means of how the consortium will reach those audiences:

¹ http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/portal/desktop/en/support/reference_terms.html

² http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/other/gm/h2020-guide-comm_en.pdf

Research Community

- *Events:* The consortium organized networking events to foster mind-set change to apply AI in the Digitalized Industry. The high scientific profile of the participating academic and research institutes guaranteed the success of these special issues, which will demonstrate the project's research achievements worldwide; furthermore, the three key networking workshops were organized to co-inside with other annual large-scale events;
- *Workshops organization:* The consortium organized online and live workshops and webinars throughout the project's duration, where interested researchers and industry professionals could join and learn about AI and its advances;
- *Contribution to international journals and conferences:* All the interesting and innovative research results of AI4DI were published in leading international journals in the field, as well as presented to international conferences. This resulted in 118 peer-reviewed publications in books, journals and conference proceedings. It must be pointed out that all principal investigators from research and academia involved in AI4DI comprise well-recognised experts in their field and they participate in wider associations in their fields of expertise, ensuring this way the successful dissemination of AI4DI results and research findings.

Industrial and Business Audiences

The AI4DI has a group of industrial partners, SMEs, and public bodies, with strong networking profiles, which led the dissemination of the project's outcomes to the industry. This was achieved through direct dissemination activities such as e-marketing campaigns, news groups, mailing lists, social media, online press and on-site promotions. Furthermore, dissemination through partners' web sites, with their experiences of this solution and the high level of service provided by the AI4DI platform was ensured. Exhibitions and participation in specialised events, forums and platforms, in which a number of the project's consortium are prominent members of, guaranteed a wide dissemination of the results in EUs scientific and innovative business scenes. Finally, indirect dissemination was accomplished via consortium partners' public relations, word of mouth, articles and assessment written by independent reviewers.

General Public

- *Traditional Dissemination* including website, newsletters, social media, flyers, and periodicals;
- Written articles and papers for publications, engaging in public speaking events;
- Encourage blogger groups to write about the AI4DI solution and establish a social media presence (e.g. Twitter and LinkedIn).

6 Dissemination and communication guidelines

To ensure that AI4DI consortium partners are familiar with, and follow the correct procedures when disseminating and communicating information about the project, common Guidelines were prepared. AI4DI Dissemination and Communication Guidelines were developed in a form of a ppt presentation, uploaded onto partner's data-share ownCloud, and presented to the consortium during conference call meetings.

Firstly, the Guidelines describe the concepts of Communication and Dissemination, in the framework of ECSEL JU funding and Horizon 2020 programme. Then the subsequent information follows:

6.1 Acknowledgement of funding and disclaimer

The appropriate ways of acknowledging funding and funding programmes are described in the AI4DI Dissemination and Communication Guidelines. Partners are able to choose the most appropriate form to use to insert into their publications, presentations, and other dissemination and communication means. The following acknowledgement of funding information is used by the consortium:

- Acknowledgement of funding must be included in all AI4DI-related publications and other dissemination material:

“AI4DI receives funding within the Electronic Components and Systems for European Leadership Joint Undertaking (ECSEL JU) in collaboration with the European Union’s Horizon2020 Framework Programme and National Authorities, under grant agreement n° 826060.”

- Alternative acknowledgement texts:

“The work/A part of the work has been performed in the project AI4DI: Artificial Intelligence for Digitizing Industry, under grant agreement No 826060. The project is co-funded by grants from Germany, Austria, Finland, France, Norway, Latvia, Belgium, Italy, Switzerland, and Czech Republic and - Electronic Component Systems for European Leadership Joint Undertaking (ECSEL JU).”

“AI4DI project has received funding from the ECSEL Joint Undertaking (JU) under grant agreement No 826060. The JU receives support from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme. It is co-funded by the consortium members and grants from Germany, Austria, Finland, France, Norway, Latvia, Belgium, Italy, Switzerland, and Czech Republic.”

- ECSEL JU logo and the European Union flag must be visible next to the acknowledgement of the funding sources:

- National or regional funding authorities must be acknowledged, and their logos included where possible:

- Furthermore, any dissemination and communication activities need to adhere to the specific conditions of EU funding and disclaimer according to Article 38.1.3, which is excluding [Agency and] Commission responsibility. Thus, the following disclaimer is included in the communication material where appropriate:

“All AI4DI-related communication reflects only the author’s view and the [Agency and the] Commission are not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.”

6.2 Social media posting guidelines

After information about acknowledgement of funding, the AI4DI Dissemination and Communication Guidelines describe where partners can find the dissemination materials (such as presentations, templates, posters). This is followed by **social media posting guidelines**, described below:

AI4DI consortium uses Twitter account **@AI4DI** for social media presence.

What we post: Texts of up to **280** characters. This excludes media attachments (photos, images, videos, etc.) and quoted tweets (displaying someone else’s tweet within your own) but includes links (a URL is always altered to 23 characters).

How we use it: To share short comments, make announcements that can instantaneously reach a large audience or retweet relevant content, post pictures from events and videos of demonstrators.

The account is also embedded in the project website www.AI4DI.eu and shares content with the AI4DI LinkedIn account <https://www.linkedin.com/company/ai4di/>.

The following terminology is important:

Hashtag # - a hashtag is added in front of any word or phrase in a post, this makes it easier for users to locate our specific content. Examples of applicable hashtags are the following: #Innovation, #AI, #futuretechnologies, #industry, #KDT, #ECSELJU, #AI, #digitisingindustries, #edge, and others. Using a hashtag makes the keyword or phrase in the post searchable. It is like a label that clusters and links similar content, the same way keywords do when scientific papers are published. They are used to increase outreach – enabling us to join bigger, topic-specific conversations, to capitalize on existing trends, to consolidate and group content – helping those who took part in an event search for related coverage using the event’s hashtag, to encourage interaction.

Handle @ - unique handle / user name used to identify AI4DI project’s account. It always starts with the @ symbol, followed by a name to identify the account: **@AI4DI**. We use handles to mention partner organizations, funding organizations, and related projects, to send a direct reply to someone, by starting our message with their handle, and to link to someone else’s account (known as a 'mention') by using their handle in our post.

Tone and general notes that our consortium takes into account when posting in social media:

- Never post pictures or text containing confidential information from consortium’s internal meetings;
- Use appropriate, inoffensive language (to ensure we get responses and stimulate debate);
- Be receptive to our readers’ arguments – if we don't agree, we can defend our position without being rude;
- Gain/maintain credibility by sharing worthwhile, relevant content and show respect for other cultures and ideas, online as well as offline;
- We must be aware that libel and defamation laws apply;
- We created our **project handle** and use it consistently throughout the overall project implementation;
- If the partners, researchers, team members or other relevant organizations already have a strong, well established social media presence, we encourage them to **communicate information about our** project;
- Use handles, such as **@ECSELJU** and **@KDT** in our tweets to maximize visibility and be recognized as part of the ECSEL JU and KDT community;
- Twitter is becoming increasingly **visual** – we post pictures, videos or data visualizations to spark interest;
- Share images and **tag other Twitter accounts** (up to 10), to build a relationship with your audience and make them aware (the account tagged receives a notification) of content that might interest them, in the hope that they might want to retweet it.

The following posting schedule is observed for AI4DI Twitter and website posts:

TABLE 2 AI4DI SOCIAL MEDIA AND WEBSITE POSTING SCHEDULE

	Twitter	Website
ON THE DAY OF REGISTRATION TO EVENT	HEADLINE, EVENT DETAILS, LINK	
2 DAYS PRIOR TO EVENT	HEADLINE, EVENT DETAILS, LINK	
DURING EVENT	PHOTOS, LIVE DETAILS	
2 DAYS AFTER EVENT		SUMMARY OF EVENT, RESULTS, PHOTOS
PUBLIC PROJECT RESULTS	HEADLINE, DETAILS, PARTNER INFORMATION	HEADLINE, DETAILS, PARTNER INFORMATION
PROJECT NEWSLETTER	HEADLINE, NEWSLETTER	HEADLINE, NEWSLETTER

6.3 Data Management Plan

In large project like AI4DI with nearly 200 member-users, it is important to enable a smooth operation, safe data exchange and effective management of data among the members. To reach these goals, the AI4DI consortium uses a cloud platform for the data-exchange, where the confidential sharing of files is possible without restrictions. This information below lists the public-information of the Data Management Plan.

6.3.1 Data Exchange Platform Nextcloud

The uses cloud software is the so-called “Nextcloud”, (see Figure below: Screenshot of the AI4DI data share Nextcloud), installed on a server and hosted from the OTH-AW.

FIGURE 1 AI4DI DATA SHARE NEXTCLOUD

6.3.1.1 Access

The Nextcloud-server software supports fully the WebDAV protocol, so users can connect to the server and synchronize their working data. This is possible with every standard browser like, Firefox, Internet Explorer, Opera or Chrome, through the link <https://AI4DI-cloud.automotive.oth-aw.de/> so no additional software is needed to install for the users. It is also possible to access by client applications, which are available for all common Windows, Mac and Linux and furthermore by mobile apps for iOS and Android. It is not necessary to install the apps, but they facilitate the working with files, so they are automatically synchronized properly after saving. The client can be configured to store the data on any local directory.

The files are shared within the project AI4DI, but it is also possible to create personal data, which is not shared.

The file size is partly limited to 512 MB, but can be extended to bigger files if necessary. There are no restrictions for the upload/download speed of the connected users

6.3.1.2 Safety and Security

Within the Nextcloud a version control allows to access to older versions of the files. The Nextcloud software is updated frequently to keep the system up-to-date.

A daily backup is made from all data, which are physically separated from the server. The server is located in Germany at the OTH-AW.

The access to the files is only allowed through the https-protocol [HTTPS]. After the login to the Nextcloud all communication is protected through an SSL encrypted access, verified by a CA-certificate.

6.3.1.3 Mailing lists

Mailing lists for the efficient communication among project partners were set-up; the following lists are available:

members@AI4DI.eu (entire Consortium)

core@AI4DI.eu (Project management team)

SC-Leader@AI4DI.eu

WP-Leader@AI4DI.eu

WP1@AI4DI.eu

WP2@AI4DI.eu

WP3@AI4DI.eu

WP4@AI4DI.eu

WP5@AI4DI.eu

WP6@AI4DI.eu

WP7@AI4DI.eu

WP8@AI4DI.eu

The members@AI4DI.eu list is the largest list, with more than 200 users and is therefore restricted in sending for project management team members to avoid the spamming with reply-mails to the users. All other lists are free in the usage and all members can post mails to it.

The members of all lists are daily updated to keep the lists up to date.

6.3.1.4 Server configuration

The web site and the data-exchange platform are hosted on a server located at the OTH-AW (Ostbayerische Technische Hochschule Amberg-Weiden) in Germany, Amberg. The connection provides all needed features like unlimited file upload, not restricted by size or speed. The server has a 1 Gbit/s uplink, which is guarded against failure by a 1Gbit/s secondary backup link. The server is driven by a containerized structure with access through reverse proxies for nextcloud and Joomla. All systems are frequently updated.

The member management for the Nextcloud is combined within the Joomla! backend.

6.3.2 Data privacy and security

The project partners agree that any Background, Results, Confidential Information and/or any and all data and/or information that is provided, disclosed or otherwise made available between the project partners during the implementation of the Action and/or for any Exploitation activities (“Shared Information”), shall not include personal data as defined by Article 2, Section (a) of the Data Protection Directive (95/46/EEC) and applicable local implementing local legislation; or, as from May, 25th 2018, Article 4 of the General Data Protection Regulation. The Data Protection Directive, its implementing local legislation and the General Data Protection Regulation are hereinafter collectively referred to as the Data Protection Legislation.

Accordingly, each project partner will ensure that all data and information contained in Shared Information is anonymised such that it is no longer personal data, prior to providing the Shared

Information to such other Parties. Each project partner who provides or otherwise makes Shared Information available to any other project partner, (“Contributor”) represents that, as per applicable Data Protection Legislation: (i) it has the authority to disclose the Shared Information, if any, which it provides to the project partners under the Consortium Agreement; (ii) where legally required and relevant, it has a legal ground to provide the Shared Information; and (iii) there is no restriction in place that would prevent any such other project partner from using the Shared Information for the purpose of this Action and the exploitation thereof.

6.3.3 Open Access publishing guidelines

The AI4DI consortium embraces the vision that large and unrestricted access to knowledge is essential not only for the central role of knowledge and innovation in generating growth but also as a fundamental human value of scientific knowledge progress and dissemination. In line with the “Guidelines on Open Access to Scientific Publications and Research Data in Horizon 2020”, the project beneficiaries aim to ensure open access (‘gold’, or ‘green’) to all peer-reviewed publications relating to the project results. Authors’ copyrights agreements will determine whether scientific publications, resulted from the project, adopt the gold or the green model. However, in the case copyright agreements are not violated (e.g. in the case of peer reviewed journals and international conference proceedings), the consortium favours whichever model guarantees wider dissemination of the project results. Therefore, the AI4DI project’s Dissemination and Communication Guidelines describe the principles of Open Access Publishing. To comply with the AI4DI project’s Grant Agreement, consortium partners make their papers and presentations available to the entire consortium ahead of publication; they must be emailed to consortium’s Dissemination Manager or the Core Team, and then subsequently shared with the entire consortium.

AI4DI Consortium Agreement states the following: “8.4.2.1 Prior notice of conference contributions and oral/poster presentations (PowerPoint presentations or similar) shall be given by the Party or Parties proposing the dissemination to by email [...] at least 21 calendar days before submission (contributions) or presentation (presentations). Any objection to such planned publication shall be made in accordance with the Grant Agreement in writing to the Coordinator and to the Party or Parties proposing the dissemination within 14 calendar days after receipt of the notice. [...] Prior notice of any other planned publication shall be given by the Party or Parties proposing the dissemination by email to the other Parties at least 45 calendar days before submission. Any objection to the planned publication shall be made in accordance with the Grant Agreement in writing to the Coordinator and to the Party or Parties proposing the dissemination within 30 calendar days after receipt of the notice. If no objection is made within the time limit stated above, the publication is permitted.”

Consortium partners followed the review and approval process described in the subsequent process illustration:

FIGURE 2 AI4DI PUBLICATION AND PRESENTATION REVIEW AND APPROVAL PROCESS

Under Horizon2020, each beneficiary must ensure open access to all peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to its results, and AI4DI consortium partners are all expected and informed to follow these rules. Each partner must - at the very least - ensure that their publications can be read online, downloaded and printed. Partners make every effort to have additional rights such as the right to copy, distribute, search, link, crawl, and mine increase the utility of the accessible publication. Consortium partners follow the **AI4DI Open Access Guideline Presentation**, which was distributed to the entire consortium and is available on the projects file-share ownCloud. More information is also available at: [Open access & Data management – SEDIA Guide](#)

7 Dissemination and communication strategy deployment

AI4DI consortium partners focused on the following types of activities to communicate and disseminate information about the AI4DI:

Events-based communication: Awareness-raising regarding AI4DI was impacted positively by active presence in international conferences (online and in person), workshops, demonstrations, webinars - and the organisation of three project co-organised events in the duration of the project. The AI4DI representation took place in different ways:

- AI4DI organised physical and virtual events (e.g. AI4DI Bologna Symposium, AI4DI webinars, International Workshop on Edge Artificial Intelligence for Industrial Applications (EAI4IA), and Embedded Artificial Intelligence (EAI) – Devices, Systems, and Industrial Applications workshop);
- Participated in major events with targeted stakeholders, using project booth and posters (EFCS, Graz Symposium Virtual Vehicle, and others).
- Participated in key events for liaising or networking purposes (IOT Week, Industry 4.0, The Autonomous, and other annual events).

Web-based communication.: Online activities, including social networks (Twitter and LinkedIn) designed as central to the project website and geared completely towards raising awareness and traffic by encouraging more people to visit the AI4DI website;

Print -based communication: newsletters, journals, posters, brochure, leaflets etc.;

Audio-visual communication: Prepare a campaign video (simple, for the general public to understand) promoting the project and upload it to the Projects Website, as well as to Vimeo and social media platforms; prepare videos of the project’s technological demonstrators;

Mailings: Promoting AI4DI will be supported by the efficient use of tools such as mailing/distribution lists, which can raise awareness and allow regular contact (e-newsletter).

7.1 Events-based communication

Awareness-raising regarding AI4DI project was impacted positively by project representation in relevant events. Consortium partners represented the project at a number of events aiming to promote the AI4DI outputs and to disseminate by all appropriate means and tools, all relevant information that raises public awareness about the consortium’s work. Participation in events was also an opportunity to increase and strengthen the network of relevant parties interested in becoming multipliers of AI4DI.

Below is a list of some of the most impactful, key events and conferences in the area of AI research, where AI4DI was presented and/or was present (AI4DI-organised events are highlighted in blue):

TABLE 3 DISSEMINATION EVENTS’ CALENDAR

Event name	Date	Location	Notes
Innovation Drift 2019	2019 07 13-14	Vilnius	-
ECSEL JU Symposium 2019	2019 06 17-18	Bucharest	booth, poster
IECON 2019 – 45 th Annual Conference of the IEEE Industrial Electronics Society	2019 10 14-17	Lisbon	Publication
EF ECS 2019 – European Forum for Electronic Components and Systems	2019 11 19-20	Helsinki	booth, poster
ECSEL–Austria Conference "ECSEL-Austria – A success story moves on"	2019 11 27	Graz	Presentation
HiPEAC 2020	2020 01 20-22	Bologna	-
AI4DI Symposium Bologna 2020	2020 01 23	Bologna	presentation, poster, panel discussions
Smart City MINDTREK 2020	2020 01 28-30	Tampere	Presentation
24 th Conference on Automation	2020 03 18-20	Warsaw	Publication
ECSEL JU Symposium 2020	2020 06 24	online	-

PCIM Europe 2020	2020 07 7-8	Nuremberg	Presentation
2 nd Workshop on Closing the Reality Gap in Sim2Real Transfer for Robotics	2020 07 12	online	Publications
The 23 rd IEEE International Conference on Intelligent Transportation Systems	2020 09 20-23	online	Publication
33 rd International Conference on Industrial, Engineering & Other Applications of Applied Intelligent Systems (IEA/AIE)	2020 09 22-25	Kitakyushu, Japan	Publication
European Research and Innovation Days	2020 09 22-24	online	-
LOGIN 2020	2020 09 24	Vilnius	-
IEEE IECON 2020 conference	2020 10 18-21	Singapore; online	Publication
EuWoRel 2020	2020 10 21-22	Berlin	-
Industrie 4.0 Conference Kaunas	2020 10 27	Kaunas	Leaflet
ECA2030 Conference	2020 10 27-28	online	-
4 th International Conference nanoFIS 2020	2020 11 2-4	online	-
AI4DI 1 st WEBINAR	2020 12 04	online	presentation, success stories, keynote speeches
EF ECS 2020	2020 11 25-26	online	online booth, videos
AI4DI 2 nd WEBINAR	2021 03 26	online	presentation, success stories, keynote speeches
ECS Brokerage Event 2021	2021 01 13-14	online	-
HiPEAC 2021	2021 01 18-20	online	Publication
AI Safety 2020	2022 07 26	Vienna	Publication
Design, Automation, and Test in Europe (DATE) Conference 2021	2021 02 01-05	online	Publication
AI4DI 3 rd WEBINAR	2021 05 11	online	presentation, success stories, keynote speeches
ESI Symposium	2021 04 20	Veldhoven	-
Industry Strategy Symposium Europe (ISS Europe)	2021 04 21-23	Brussels	Publication
Smart Systems Integration Conference and Exhibition 2021	2021 04 27-29	Grenoble	Publication

ECSEL JU Symposium 2021	2021 06 30	online	-
5 th International Conference nanoFIS 2022	2022 07 05-08	Aveiro	Publication
The 24 th IEEE International Conference on Intelligent Transportation Systems	2021 09 19-22	USA	Publication
EF ECS 2021	2021 11 23	online	booth, poster, videos
HiPEAC 2022	2022 06 20-22	Budapest	-
16th International Conference "Mechatronic Systems and Materials"	2021 08 01	Vilnius	Presentation
SIDO2021	2021 09 14-15	Lyon	Demo booth to showcase the Pommery demonstrator
Xecs Launch event	2021 09 28	online	Attendance
EPoSS Annual Forum 2021	2021 10 04	Freiburg im Breisgau, Germany	Attendance
EuWoRel 2021. The 9th European expert workshop on reliability of electronics and smart systems	2021 10 12	Berlin, Germany	Attendance
SEMICON Europa	2021 10 17	Munich, Germany	Attendance
EBSCON: Electronic Based Systems Conference	2021 11 04	Graz, Austria	Attendance
Entrepreneur event	2021 11 12	Mäntsälä, Finland	Automated transport development
Webinar Robots and Automation	2021 11 14	online, Live on Facebook	Presentation Robots and automation - a threat or an opportunity!?
AEIT AUTOMOTIVE 2021	2021 11 17-19	online	-
Future Professionals seminar	2021 11 25	Kouvola, Finland	Presentation
TMC@IMC Distinguished Lecture Series	30.11.2021	online	Presentation
IWES	2021 12 09-10	Roma	Presentation
Material Research Society 2022 Spring Meeting	2022 05 08-13	Honolulu, Hawai'i	Presentation

IEEE 9th International Conference on Computational Intelligence and Virtual Environments for Measurement Systems and Applications (CIVEMSA)	2022 06 15-17	Chemnitz, Germany	Presentation
EAIISA 2022 Workshop on Edge AI for Smart Agriculture	2022 06 20-23	Biarritz, France	Presentation
IEEE International Conference on Edge Computing and Communications (EDGE)	2022 07 11-16	online / Barcelona, Spain	Presentation
SciPy 2022 conference	2022 07 11-17	Austin, TX (USA)	Presentation
International Workshop on Edge Artificial Intelligence for Industrial Applications (EAI4IA)	2022 07 25-26	Vienna	workshop, presentation, co-organisation
International Workshop on Embedded Artificial Intelligence (EAI) – Devices, Systems, and Industrial Applications.	2022 09 19	Milan	workshop, presentation, co-organisation
Inter.noise 2022	2022 08 21-14	Glasgow, UK	Presentation
ESSIRC Workshop	2022 09 19	Milan	workshop, attendance
European Material Research Society Fall Meeting	2022 09 20-23	Virtual	Presentation
IEEE 18th International Conference on Intelligent Computer Communication and Processing	2022 09 22-24	Cluj-Napoca, Romania	Presentation
Workshop during the Trends and Applications of Answer Set Programming Workshop	2022 11 28-29	Vienna	workshop, presentation
EF ECS 2022	2022 11 24-25	Amsterdam	booth, poster, videos, leaflets, roll-up poster, visualisations

Overall, AI4DI project was presented in over 60 high-impact events, some of which were co-organised by the consortium partners. Over 100 events in total were attended, where the AI4DI partners discussed the project with key stakeholders, presented the project's aims and results, disseminated as word-of-mouth, and ensured a wide outreach.

FIGURE 1 AI4DI PROJECT AT KEY EVENTS THROUGHOUT THE PROJECT'S LIFETIME

7.1.1 AI4DI Symposium Bologna

AI4DI consortium organised a high-level international workshop and symposium for consortium members and guests in Bologna at the beginning of 2020, for a three-day event of project's technical meeting, vision meeting, and the AI4DI Symposium.

The 22nd of January 2020 was dedicated to project's internal technical meetings, addressing the developments in the Supply Chains and following the activities defined in Work Package 2 'System Level Design for Industrial AI Solutions'.

The second day of the gathering, the 23rd of January, was dedicated for a large-scale AI4DI Symposium, titled 'AI for Digitising Industry Symposium – Exploring the Future (AI4DIS 2020)'. Over 100 attendees gathered for the Symposium, and this event became an impressive venue for researchers, scientists, system developers, manufacturers, practitioners, and standardization experts to share a joint interest in the research and developments of AI, embedded systems, communication, and IIoT technologies for the digital transformation of industry.

FIGURE 2 AI4DI SYMPOSIUM 2020 BOLOGNA

7.1.2 AI4DI International Workshop on Edge Artificial Intelligence for Industrial Applications (EAI4IA)

The International Workshop on Edge Artificial Intelligence for Industrial Applications (EAI4IA) is co-located with the 31st International Joint Conference on Artificial Intelligence and the 23rd European Conference on Artificial Intelligence (**IJCAI-ECAI 2022**) to be held in Vienna, Austria, in July 2022. EAI4IA aims to bring together researchers and practitioners working on providing edge artificial intelligence methods, techniques and tools to be used in industrial applications. EAI4IA comprises technical presentations, keynotes and panel discussions focusing on industrial-edge AI hardware, software and AI frameworks.

On the following day, July 27th, the AI4DI consortium met for an internal technical meeting as well.

EAI4IA was a multidisciplinary workshop addressing AI technologies at the edge, giving an overview of silicon-born AI components to advance Moore's law and accelerate the adoption of AI-based edge processing in different industries. Technological advances regarding edge AI embedded in electronic components and systems were presented, and the challenges of introducing embedded AI

technologies for digitising industrial sectors were discussed. It was co-organised by three large-scale ECSEL JU projects: **AI4DI**, **ANDANTE** and **TEMPO**.

EAI4IA comprised technical presentations, keynotes and panel discussions focusing on industrial-edge AI hardware, software and AI. Nine papers from AI4DI were accepted for presentation at the workshop. The workshop publications are bundled in an open-access book: Industrial Artificial Intelligence Technologies and Applications (riverpublishers.com).

FIGURE 3 AI4DI INTERNATIONAL WORKSHOP EAI4IA INVITATION

FIGURE 4 INTERNATIONAL WORKSHOP CO-ORGANISERS

7.1.3 AI4DI International Workshop on Embedded Artificial Intelligence (EAI) - Devices, Systems, and Industrial

The third large-scale networking and AI community building event from AI4DI was the International Workshop titled **The International Workshop on Embedded Artificial Intelligence (EAI) - Devices, Systems, and Industrial** which was co-organised by projects AI4DI, TEMPO and ANDANTE as part of the ESSCIRC ESSDERC 2022 European Solid-state Circuits and Devices Conference, and held in Milan, Italy, on the 19th of September 2022.

FIGURE 5 EAI INTERNATIONAL WORKSHOP INVITATION

This workshop brought together academics, researchers, and industry practitioners from various fields, including artificial intelligence, cyber-physical and embedded systems, microelectronics circuits and devices, edge computing, and autonomous integrated systems. Different views on today's and future embedded artificial intelligence were discussed, and the latest developments on devices, techniques, and industrial edge applications were presented. The workshop covered invited keynote talks and presentations with opportunities for researchers in the audience to interact with the speakers, discuss novel and exciting research, and establish new and fruitful collaborations in the field of embedded artificial intelligence.

The EAI workshop was co-organised by three large-scale ECSEL JU projects, **AI4DI**, **ANDANTE**, and **TEMPO**, to provide a platform to exchange knowledge and ideas among experts and professionals interested in advances in AI circuits and devices design, AI hardware architectures, industrial edge AI technologies, toolchains, and applications.

FIGURE 6 AI4DI INTERNATIONAL WORKSHOP CO-ORGANISERS

7.1.4 AI4DI Webinars

During the second half of the AI4DI project's first year of implementation, the global COVID-19 pandemic had halted nearly all mass gatherings, resulting in numerous cancellations of planned dissemination and communication events. Consortium partners reacted by creating an ongoing list with planned online events where the AI4DI project was presented. Furthermore, to compensate for the lack of 'live' events, three AI4DI Webinars were organised, attracting a cumulative audience of over 200 participants and even more views of the webinar recordings after the events.

Webinars with project supply chains were organised to report progress and adapt the dissemination strategy according to inputs received and specific needs. Webinars included a general presentation of the project goals, as well as videos, success stories, and keynote speakers. The first AI4DI Webinar was titled 'AI for Automotive Manufacturing and Mobility-as-a-Service', and the second Webinar was titled 'AI Stories for Industries (Semiconductor, Wood Machinery and Beverage/Food Production)'.

AI4DI Webinars became the key pillars in the project goal for AI community-building efforts in Europe, being complementary of other initiatives in the related field, and in building and sustaining dynamic AI technology eco systems. The webinars were open both to the most interested and invested stakeholders, representatives from other consortia, industry representatives, as well as the general public. Webinars are structured to both present the goals, achievements, success stories and the roadmap developed by the AI4DI project, and to entice and facilitate a lively discussion on the technological breakthroughs. The webinars were recorded and displayed in the project's website, to ensure that interested stakeholders who are unavailable to join the webinar in real-time, can visit the information and discussions at a time that is most convenient for them.

FIGURE 7 INVITATION TO THE FIRST AI4DI WEBINAR

INVITATION

AI for Semiconductor and Industrial Machinery Industries
26th of March 2021, 09:00-11:30 CET - Online

MACHINERY

AUTOMOTIVE MANUFACTURING

SEMICONDUCTOR MANUFACTURING

BEVERAGE INDUSTRY

TRANSPORTATION

INVITATION

AI for Smart Food and Beverage Production
11th of May 2021, 09:00-11:30 CET - Online

MACHINERY

AUTOMOTIVE MANUFACTURING

SEMICONDUCTOR MANUFACTURING

BEVERAGE INDUSTRY

TRANSPORTATION

FIGURE 8 2ND AND 3RD WEBINAR INVITATIONS

AI4DI WEBINAR no2: AI for Semiconductor and Industrial Machinery Industries
26th of March 2021

Webinar Keynote speaker Prof. Wolfgang Ecker, Infineon:

“We have to be multidisciplinary. It’s not just Artificial Intelligence, it’s application know-how, it’s process know-how, know-how of the consequences, and know-how of the technology.”

FIGURE 9 A QUOTE FROM THE AI4DI WEBINAR'S KEYNOTE SPEAKER PROF. WOLFGANG ECKER, INFINEON

7.2 Web-based communication

During the first months of the project, AI4DI project's website was created by OTH-AW. The AI4DI website is a useful tool to provide in a practical and user-friendly way the project work and dissemination material. Using the www (world wide web) grants access to every member of the project and also gives the public audience a fast and easy way to receive project information. The website is divided in two parts, public information (www.AI4DI.eu) and a project internal data exchange.

Both parts of the website are setup within a flowing process through the project members and is frequently updated with new input, e.g. news of the project, meetings, participation in events, and developments. The website is used to provide downloads of the dissemination material.

The website's design was re-made and updated significantly during the second and third years of the project, to make it even more attention-grabbing and attractive.

7.2.1 Website design

The web design was created to fulfil the corporate design, made up by the logo and the visual identity used for the internal and external project communication. This is important for the recognition factor and the continuous solid public image.

7.2.2 Project logo

The AI4DI logo depicts the title of the project combined with an illustration. The overall image is forming a brain shaped logo and at the same showing a circuit board layout. These images are combining the content of the AI4DI project, Artificial Intelligence depicted as brain and Digitizing Industries depicted as the circuits.

FIGURE 3 AI4DI LOGO – COLOURFUL AND MONOCHROME VARIATIONS

7.2.3 Website layout

The layout of the website is derived from a responsive template. It adapts and resizes itself to desktop and mobile devices and provides an optimal handling in viewing and interaction. It is comfortable in its

usage for reading, navigation, resizing, panning and scrolling and works with the commonly used range of devices, from desktop monitors.

7.2.4 Website access

The website is accessible through the URL <https://www.AI4DI.eu>. The domain name AI4DI.eu is chosen to connect to the project name AI4DI and the top-level domain .eu, which shows the reference to the European Union (EU).

7.2.5 Public Web Content

The public web content is based on the project contents and its activities. It provides details about the project information as an outcome of the project dissemination and derived from meetings and discussions among consortium members. The intention of the web site is to inform both the public and project members. The visitors vary from experts in the field, public authorities, industry representatives, researchers, and the general public.

7.2.6 Menus and submenus

The website has the following menu entries on the top site of the web site: Home, News, About the Project, Consortium, Coordinator, and 'Project Data Share' below, to navigate to other parts of the website.

FIGURE 4 HOME PAGE OF THE AI4DI WEBSITE

Furthermore, project's Twitter and LinkedIn accounts were created and is used for posting live updates, project news, and other items. Rules and guidelines for AI4DI posts in social media are described in the section 4.4.3 above. The AI4DI Twitter and LinkedIn accounts have a total cumulative number of **910 followers**.

FIGURE 10 AI4DI SOCIAL MEDIA ACCOUNTS WITH A CUMULATIVE TOTAL OF OVER 1,000 FOLLOWERS

More detailed information about the AI4DI website is described in Deliverable D7.2 'Project website'.

7.2.7 AI4DI Videos

To ensure a wide communication to both specialised and non-specialised audiences, project videos were developed. The main video of the AI4DI project describes the overall goals and aims of the project, as well as the five industry areas. It was prepared during the second year of the project, and received a wide popularity of the social media of the project and at events.

FIGURE 11 ACREENSHOTS FROM THE AI4DI ANIMATED EXPLAINER VIDEO

Additionally, a very attractive and informative animated video was developed for the description of the AI4DI project's work in the smart food and beverage industry.

FIGURE 12 SHOTS FROM THE AI4DI INFORMATION VIDEO ABOUT THE SMART FOOD AND BEVERAGE PRODUCTION

Furthermore, there are 6 Demonstrator videos prepared and uploaded on the project's social media, and 17 more demonstrator videos are in preparation. This extensive use of video material ensured an attractive, wide-spread and effective way of communicating about the project online and at events.

7.3 Print -based communication

AI4DI consortium's approach is to use the consortium's experience and knowledge of individual groups' needs to develop promotional material that can reflect the project's message and reach its target audiences through the right channels, using the appropriate content and style. The material carries the ECSEL JU and AI4DI logos which along with the visual identity creates awareness across the target audiences.

Developing these print-based products in an attractive and high-quality manner requires careful organisation and the inclusion of several sub-processes such as information gathering, analysis, and translation, among others. For this, we have developed the following visualisations, which were used for leaflets, posters, and other print-based dissemination means:

FIGURE 5 BANNER FOR AI4DI GENERAL MARKET PRESENTATION

FIGURE 6 AI4DI VISUALIZATIONS

Together with the website and leaflets, consortium’s posters for presenting results to the interested audience as well as contact information, was produced. The first version of the project poster had been prepared for the EFES2019 conference, and then the design was updated in the second and third years of the project:

FIGURE 7 AI4DI POSTER FOR THE EFCS2019 CONFERENCE AND AI4DI POSTER FOR THE 3RD YEAR OF THE PROJECT

7.4 AI4DI Publications

Throughout the project lifetime and beyond, AI4SI partners actively disseminate the results of the project’s work via peer-reviewed and other publications, in compliance with the Open Access rules. This active work **resulted in a total of 121 publications**, and more publications are still in preparation. The below table lists the publications of the project as reported in the Sygma Portal:

TABLE 4 AI4DI PUBLICATIONS

Publications for Project 826060				
No.	Type	Title	Authors	Title of the Journal/Proc./Book
1	Chapter in a Book	On the Use of Answer Set Programming for Model-Based Diagnosis	Franz Wotawa	Trends in Artificial Intelligence Theory and Applications. Artificial Intelligence Practices - 33rd International Conference on Industrial, Engineering and Other Applications of Applied Intelligent Systems, IEA/AIE 2020, Kitakyushu, Japan, September 22-25, 2020, Proceedings
2	Article in Journal	CMix-NN: Mixed Low-Precision CNN Library for Memory-Constrained Edge Devices	Alessandro Capotondi, Manuele Rusci, Marco Fariselli, Luca Benini	IEEE Transactions on Circuits and Systems II: Express Briefs
3	Publication in Conference	DORY: Lightweight memory hierarchy management for deep NN inference on IoT	Alessio Burrello, Francesco Conti, Angelo Garofalo,	Proceedings of the International Conference on Hardware/Software Codesign and System Synthesis Companion

	proceedings/Workshop	endnodes - work-in-progress	Davide Rossi, Luca Benini	
4	Article in Journal	Runtime Design Space Exploration and Mapping of DCNNs for the Ultra-Low-Power Orlando SoC	Ahmet Erdem, Cristina Silvano, Thomas Boesch, Andrea Carlo Ornstein, Surinder-Pal Singh, Giuseppe Desoli	ACM Transactions on Architecture and Code Optimization
5	Publication in Conference proceedings/Workshop	Speed Control of PMSM with Finite Control Set Model Predictive Control Using General-purpose Computing on GPU	Michal Kozubik, Pavel Vaclavek	IECON 2020 The 46th Annual Conference of the IEEE Industrial Electronics Society
6	Article in Journal	Intelligent Agents Diagnostics—Enhancing Cyber-Physical Systems with Self-Diagnostic Capabilities	David Kaufmann, Iulia Nica, Franz Wotawa	Advanced Intelligent Systems
7	Publication in Conference proceedings/Workshop	On the Use of Available Testing Methods for Verification & Validation of AI-based Software and Systems	Franz Wotawa	Proceedings of the Workshop on Artificial Intelligence Safety 2021 (SafeAI 2021) co-located with the Thirty-Fifth AAAI Conference on Artificial Intelligence (AAAI 2021)
8	Thesis/Dissertation	Realization of a Service Pipeline for Traffic Density Estimation and Prediction based on Traffic Data using Machine Learning	Ruben Prokscha	
9	Publication in Conference proceedings/Workshop	A Tile-based Fused-layer CNN Accelerator for FPGAs	F. Indirli, A. Erdem, C. Silvano	2020 27th IEEE International Conference on Electronics, Circuits and Systems (ICECS)
10	Publication in Conference proceedings/Workshop	DORY: Automatic End-to-End Deployment of Real-World DNNs on Low-Cost IoT MCUs	A. Burrello, A. Garofalo, N. Bruschi, G. Tagliavini, D. Rossi, F. Conti	IEEE Transactions on Computers
11	Publication in Conference proceedings/Workshop	Automated Diagnosis of Cyber-Physical Systems	Franz Wotawa, Oliver Tazl, and David Kaufmann	The 34th International Conference on Industrial, Engineering & Other Applications of Applied Intelligent Systems (IEA/AIE)

12	Article in Journal	Automotive Intelligence Embedded in Electric Connected Autonomous and Shared Vehicles Technology for Sustainable Green Mobility	Vermesan O, et al	Front. Future Transp
13	Chapter in a Book	Vers des Modèles IA pour l'Estimation du Rendement en Viticulture	Luiz Angelo Steffene	TERINT2021
14	Publication in Conference proceedings/Workshop	Comparison of Machine Learning and Deep Learning Methods for Grape Cluster Segmentation	Mohimont, L., et al	International Conference on Smart and Sustainable Agriculture (SSA'2021)
15	Article in Journal	XpulpNN: Enabling Energy Efficient and Flexible Inference of Quantized Neural Networks on RISC-V based IoT End Nodes	Angelo Garofalo, Giuseppe Tagliavini, Francesco Conti, Luca Benini and Davide Rossi	IEEE Transactions on Emerging Topics in Computing
16	Chapter in a Book	AI for Inbound Logistics Optimisation in Automotive Industry	Nikolaos Evangeliou, et al	Artificial Intelligence for Digitising Industry
17	Chapter in a Book	State of Health Estimation using a Temporal Convolutional Network for an Efficient Use of Retired Electric Vehicle Batteries within Second-Life Applications	Steffen Bockrath, Stefan Waldhör, Harald Ludwig, Vincent Lorentz	Artificial Intelligence for Digitising Industry
18	Chapter in a Book	AI Reshaping the Automotive Industry	Daniel Plorin	Artificial Intelligence for Digitising Industry
19	Chapter in a Book	Optimising Trajectories in Simulations with Deep Reinforcement Learning for Industrial Robots in Automotive Manufacturing	Noah Klarmann, et al	Artificial Intelligence for Digitising Industry Applications
20	Publication in Conference proceedings/Workshop	Deploying Deep Neural Networks on Edge Devices for Grape Segmentation	Roesler, M., et al	International Conference on Smart and Sustainable Agriculture
21	Chapter in a Book	Real-Time Predictive Maintenance – Artificial Neural Network Based Diagnosis	Petr Blaha, et al	Artificial Intelligence for Digitising Industry

22	Chapter in a Book	Foundations of Real-Time Predictive Maintenance with Root Cause Analysis	Franz Wotawa, et al	Artificial Intelligence for Digitising Industry
23	Chapter in a Book	Real-Time Predictive Maintenance – Model-Based, Simulation-Based and Machine Learning-Based Diagnosis	Franz Wotawa, et al	Artificial Intelligence for Digitising Industry
24	Chapter in a Book	AI-Based Knowledge Management System for Risk Assessment and Root Cause Analysis in Semiconductor Industry	Houssam Razouk, et al	Artificial Intelligence for Digitising Industry
25	Chapter in a Book	AI in Semiconductor Industry	Cristina De Luca, et al	Artificial Intelligence for Digitising Industry
26	Chapter in a Book	AI in Industrial Machinery	Giulio Urlini , Janis Arents and Antonio Latella	Artificial Intelligence for Digitising Industry
27	Chapter in a Book	Radar-Based Human-Robot Interfaces	Hans Cappelle , Ali Gorji Daronkolaei , Ing Jyh Tsang , Björn Debaille and Ilja Ocket	Artificial Intelligence for Digitising Industry
28	Chapter in a Book	Construction of a Smart Vision-Guided Robot System for Manipulation in a Dynamic Environment	Janis Arents , Modris Greitans and Bernd Lesser	
29	Chapter in a Book	Towards Fully Automated Verification of Semiconductor Technologies	Matthias Ludwig , Dinu Purice , Bernhard Lippmann, Ann-Christin Bette and Claus Lenz	Artificial Intelligence for Digitising Industry
30	Chapter in a Book	Touch Identification on Sensitive Robot Skin Using Time Domain Reflectometry and Machine Learning Methods	Pawel Kostka, et al	Artificial Intelligence for Digitising Industry
31	Chapter in a Book	Efficient Deep Learning Approach for Fault Detection in the Semiconductor Industry	Liliana Andrade , Thomas Baumela , Frédéric Pétrot , David Briand , Olivier Bichler and Marcello Coppola	Artificial Intelligence for Digitising Industry
32	Chapter in a Book	Automated Anomaly Detection Through Assembly and Packaging Process	Saad Al-Baddai , Martin Juhrisch , Jan Papadoudis , Anna Renner , Lippmann Bernhard , Cristina De Luca , Fabian Haas and	

			Wolfgang Schober	
33	Chapter in a Book	AI-Powered Collision Avoidance Safety System for Industrial Woodworking Machinery	Francesco Conti , Fabrizio Indirli , Antonio Latella, Francesco Papariello, Giacomo Michele Puglia, Felice Tecce , Giulio Urlini and Marcello Zanghieri	Artificial Intelligence for Digitising Industry
34	Chapter in a Book	Radar-Based Human-Robot Interfaces	Hans Cappelle , Ali Gorji Daronkolaei , Ing Jyh Tsang , Björn Debaille and Ilja Ocket	
35	Chapter in a Book	Construction of a Smart Vision-Guided Robot System for Manipulation in a Dynamic Environment	Janis Arents , Modris Greitans and Bernd Lesser	Artificial Intelligence for Digitising Industry
36	Chapter in a Book	Innovative Vineyards Environmental Monitoring System Using Deep Edge AI	Marcello Coppola , et al	
37	Chapter in a Book	Touch Identification on Sensitive Robot Skin Using Time Domain Reflectometry and Machine Learning Methods	Pawel Kostka, et al	
38	Chapter in a Book	AI in Food and Beverage Industry	Rachel Ouviaha de Oliveira , Marcello Coppola and Ovidiu Vermesan	
39	Chapter in a Book	AI-Driven Yield Estimation Using an Autonomous Robot for Data Acquisition	Lucas Mohimont, et al	Artificial Intelligence for Digitising Industry
40	Chapter in a Book	Innovative Vineyards Environmental Monitoring System Using Deep Edge AI	Marcello Coppola , et al	Artificial Intelligence for Digitising Industry

41	Chapter in a Book	AI-Based Quality Control System at the Pressing Stages of the Champagne Production	Lucas Mohimont, et al	Artificial Intelligence for Digitising Industry
42	Chapter in a Book	AI-Based Vehicle Systems for Mobility-as-a-Service Application	Mikko Tarkiainen, et al	Artificial Intelligence for Digitising Industry
43	Publication in Conference proceedings/Workshop	Report Classification for Semiconductor Failure Analysis	Frederik Platter; Anna Safont-Andreu; Christian Burmer; Konstantin Schekotihin	
44	Chapter in a Book	Applications of AI in Transportation Industry	Mathias Schneider, Matti Kutila and Alfred Höß	
45	Chapter in a Book	Open Traffic Data for Mobility-as-a-Service Applications – Architecture and Challenges	Mathias Schneider, et al	Artificial Intelligence for Digitising Industry
46	Chapter in a Book	AI and IIoT-based Predictive Maintenance System for Soybean Processing	Ovidiu Vermesan, et al	Artificial Intelligence For Digitising Industry
47	Publication in Conference proceedings/Workshop	Using Ontologies in Failure Analysis	Anna Safont-Andreu; Christian Burmer; Konstantin Schekotihin	
48	Chapter in a Book	Optimisation of Soybean Manufacturing Process Using Real-time Artificial Intelligence of Things Technology	Ovidiu Vermesan , Jøran Edell Martinsen , Anders Kristoffersen , Roy Bahr , Ronnie Otto Bellmann, Torgeir Hjertaker , John Breiland , Karl Andersen, Hans Erik Sand , Parsa Rahmanpour and David Lindberg	Artificial Intelligence for Digitising Industry
49	Chapter in a Book	AI-Driven Yield Estimation Using an Autonomous Robot for Data Acquisition	Lucas Mohimont , Luiz Angelo Steffene , Mathias Roesler , Nathalie Gaveau , Marine Rondeau , François Alin , Clément Pierlot , Rachel Ouvinha	

			de Oliveira and Marcello Coppola	
50	Other	KI-basierte Optimierung von Daten-Pipelines	Ruben Prokscha, Mathias Schneider, Seifeddine Saadani, Dr.-Ing. Alfred Höß	
51	Article in Journal	Vega: A Ten-Core SoC for IoT Endnodes With DNN Acceleration and Cognitive Wake-Up From MRAM-Based State-Retentive Sleep Mode	D. Rossi, F. Conti, M. Eggiman, A. Di Mauro, G. Tagliavini, S. Mach, M. Guermandi, A. Pullini, I. Loi, J. Chen, E. Flamand, L. Benini	IEEE Journal of Solid-State Circuits
52	Article in Journal	Advanced Applications of Industrial Robotics: New Trends and Possibilities	Andrius Dzedzickis, Jurga Subaciute-Žemaitiene, Ernestas Šutinys, Urte Samukaite-Bubniene and Vytautas Bucinskas	Applied Sciences
53	Article in Journal	Traitement d'Images et Apprentissage Automatique pour la Viticulture de Précision	Lucas Mohimont; Amine Chemchem ; Marine Rondeau ; Mathias Roesler ; François Alin ; Nathalie Gaveau ; Luiz Angelo Steffene	Revue Ouverte d'Intelligence Artificielle
55	Article in Journal	Smart Industrial Robot Control Trends, Challenges and Opportunities within Manufacturing	Janis Arents and Modris Greitans	Applied Sciences
56	Article in Journal	A TinyML Platform for On-Device Continual Learning With Quantized Latent Replays	L. Ravaglia, M. Rusci, D. Nadalini, A. Capotondi, L. Benini	IEEE Journal on Emerging and Selected Topics in Circuits and Systems
57	Other	Graph Neural Networks for Relational Inductive Bias in Vision-based Deep Reinforcement Learning of Robot Control	Oliva, Marco, Soubarna Banik, Josip Josifovski, and Alois Knoll.	

58	Publication in Conference proceedings/Workshop	Effective Use of BERT in Graph Embeddings for Sparse Knowledge Graph Completion	Xinglan Liu, Hussain Hussain, Houssam Razouk, Roman Kern	SAC '22: Proceedings of the 37th ACM/SIGAPP Symposium on Applied Computing
59	Article in Journal	Model-based reasoning using answer set programming	Franz Wotawa and David Kaufmann	Applied Intelligence
60	Article in Journal	An Intelligent Real-Time Edge Processing Maintenance System for Industrial Manufacturing, Control, and Diagnostic	Ovidiu Vermesan, Marcello Coppola, Roy Bahr, Ronnie Otto Bellmann, Jøran Edell Martinsen, Anders Kristoffersen, Torgeir Hjertaker, John Breiland, Karl Andersen, Hans Erik Sand and David Lindberg	Frontiers in Chemical Engineering
61	Publication in Conference proceedings/Workshop	Acceptance of mobility as a service by car users	Risto Öörni	14th ITS European Congress
62	Publication in Conference proceedings/Workshop	AI-Based Edge Acquisition, Processing and Analytics for Industrial Food Production	Ovidiu VERMESAN, Ronnie Otto BELLMANN, Roy BAHR, Jøran Edell MARTINSEN, Anders KRISTOFFERSEN, Torgeir Hjertaker, John Breiland, Karl Andersen, Hans Erik SAND and David LINDBERG	18th International Conference on Intelligent Environments IE2022
63	Publication in Conference proceedings/Workshop	Analysis of Randomization Effects on Sim2Real Transfer in Reinforcement Learning for Robotic Manipulation Tasks	Josifovski, J.; Malmir, M.; Klarmann, N.; Zagar, B.L.; Navarro Guerrero, N.; Knoll	IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems (IROS)

64	Publication in Conference proceedings/Workshop	AI-Based Edge Acquisition, Processing and Analytics for Industrial Food Production	Ovidiu VERMESAN, Ronnie Otto BELLMANN, Roy BAHR, Jøran Edell MARTINSEN, Anders KRISTOFFERSEN, Torgeir Hjertaker, John Breiland, Karl Andersen, Hans Erik SAND and David LINDBERG	IEEE INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON EDGE COMPUTING & COMMUNICATIONS
65	Publication in Conference proceedings/Workshop	ECBA-MLI: Edge Computing Benchmark Architecture for Machine Learning Inference	Mathias Schneider, Ruben Prokscha, Seifeddine Saadani, and Alfred Höß	2022 IEEE International Conference on Edge Computing and Communications (EDGE)
66	Publication in Conference proceedings/Workshop	Graph Neural Networks for Relational Inductive Bias in Vision-based Deep Reinforcement Learning of Robot Control	Oliva, M., Banik, S., Josifovski, J., & Knoll,	International Joint Conference on Neural Networks (IJCNN) 2022
67	Publication in Conference proceedings/Workshop	S2ORC-SemiCause: Annotating and analysing causality in the semiconductor domain	Xing Lan Liu, Eileen Salhofer, Anna Safont Andreu, Roman Kern	International Workshop on Edge Artificial Intelligence for Industrial Applications
68	Publication in Conference proceedings/Workshop	Impact of Training Instance Selection on Domain-Specific Entity Extraction using BERT	Eileen Salhofer, Xing Lan Liu, Roman Kern	North American Chapter of the Association for Computational Linguistics: Human Language Technologies: Student Research Workshop
69	Article in Journal	A Motion Capture and Imitation Learning Based Approach to Robot Control	Peteris Racinskis, Janis Arents and Modris Greitans	Applied Sciences
70	Publication in Conference proceedings/Workshop	synthetic data of randomly piled, similar objects for deep learning-based object detection	Janis Arents, Bernd Lesser, Andis Bizuns, Roberts Kadikis, Elvijs Buls and Modris Greitans	

71	Article in Journal	Improving Industrial Robot Positioning Accuracy to the Microscale Using Machine Learning Method	Vytautas Bucinskas, Andrius Dzedzickis, Marius Sumanas, Ernestas Sutiny's, Sigitas Petkevicius, Jurate Butkiene, Darius Virzonis and Inga Morkvenaite-Vilkonciene	Machines
72	Article in Journal	A review on AI Safety in highly automated driving	Wäschle, Moritz and Thaler, Florian and Berres, Axel and Pözlbauer, Florian and Albers, Albert	Frontiers in Artificial Intelligence
73	Article in Journal	Accurate effective harmonic potential treatment of the high-temperature cubic phase of Hafnia	Sebastian Bichelmaier, Jesús Carrete, Michael Nelhiebel, Georg K. H. Madsen	physica status solidi (RRL) – Rapid Research Letters
74	Publication in Conference proceedings/Workshop	Integrating multiple observation sets into consistency-based diagnosis	Franz Wotawa	International Workshop on Principles of Diagnosis (DX)
75	Publication in Conference proceedings/Workshop	DDMin versus QuickXplain – An Experimental Comparison of two Algorithms for Minimizing Collections	Oliver A. Tazl, Christopher Tafeit, Franz Wotawa, and Alexander Felfernig	Proceedings of the International Conference on Software Engineering and Knowledge Engineering (SEKE)
76	Chapter in a Book	A Framework for Integrating Automated Diagnosis into Simulation	David Kaufmann and Franz Wotawa	Industrial Artificial Intelligence Technologies and Applications
77	Chapter in a Book	On the Verification of Diagnosis Models	Franz Wotawa and Oliver Tazl	Industrial Artificial Intelligence Technologies and Applications
78	Publication in Conference proceedings/Workshop	Optimizing 3D object detection for embedded systems in automated vehicles using sensor data fusion and CUDA computing	Topi Miekkala, Matti Kutila, Mathias Schneider and Alfred Höß	
79	Publication in Conference proceedings/Workshop	A BERT-Based Report Classification for Semiconductor Failure Analysis	Corinna Grabner; Anna Safont-Andreu; Christian Burmer; Konstantin Schekotihin	

80	Article in Journal	Accurate First-Principles Treatment of the High-Temperature Cubic Phase of Hafnia	Sebastian Bichelmaier, Jesús Carrete, Michael Nelhiesel, Georg K. H. Madsen	Wiley Online Library
81	Article in Journal	Improving the Consistency of the Failure Mode Effect Analysis (FMEA) Documents in Semiconductor Manufacturing	Houssam Razouk, Roman Kern	Applied Sciences
82	Thesis/Dissertation	Application of machine learning in Microelectromechanical systems (MEMS) manufacturing	Kamil Marwat	
83	Publication in Conference proceedings/Workshop	Towards the knowledge reuse in the semiconductor manufacturing industry AI Approaches: pitfall and tips	Razouk H. and Kern R.	European apc m Conference
84	Publication in Conference proceedings/Workshop	Continual Learning on Incremental Simulations for Real-World Robotic Manipulation Tasks	Josip Josifovski, Mohammadhosse in Malmir, Noah Klarmann, Alois Knoll	
85	Publication in Conference proceedings/Workshop	Robust Sim2Real Transfer by Learning Deep Inverse Dynamics Model of Simulation	Mohammadhosse in Malmir, Josip Josifovski, Noah Klarmann, Alois Knoll	
86	Publication in Conference proceedings/Workshop	Benchmarking Automotive LiDAR Performance in Arctic Conditions	Matti Kutila, Pasi Pyykönen, Maria Jokela, Tobias Gruber, Mario Bijelic, Werner Ritter	
87	Publication in Conference proceedings/Workshop	A Fully Automated Process for Semiconductor Technology Identification	Matthias Ludwig, Bernhard Lippmann, Ann-Christin Bette, Claus Lenz	
88	Other	Testumgebung für Edge Computing in Intelligenten Transportsystemen (ITS)	Mathias Schneider, Seifeddine Saadani, Ruben Prokscha, Alfred Höß	

89	Chapter in a Book	Touch Identification on Sensitive Robot Skin Using Time Domain Reflectometry.	Pawel Kostka; Anja Winkler; Adnan Haidar; Muhammad Ghufan Khan; Rene Jäkel; Peter Winkler; Ralph Müller-Pfefferkorn	Artificial Intelligence for Digitising Industry–Applications
90	Chapter in a Book	Industrial AI Technologies for Next-Generation Autonomous Operations with Sustainable Performance	Ovidiu Vermesan, Frédéric Pétrot, Marcello Coppola, Mathias Schneider, and Alfred Höß	Intelligent Edge-Embedded Technologies for Digitising Industry
91	Chapter in a Book	Technology and Hardware for Neuromorphic Computing	Björn Debaillie, Ilya Ocket, and Peter Debacker	Intelligent Edge-Embedded Technologies for Digitising Industry
92	Chapter in a Book	Tools and Methodologies for Training, Profiling, and Mapping a Neural Network on a Hardware Target	Alexandre Valentian, Simon Narduzzi, Muhammad Arsalan, Kay Bierzynski, Stefano Traferro, Preetha Vijayan, Amirreza Yousefzadeh, Manolis Sifalakis, Rene Van Leuken, Dylan Muir, Rashid Ali, Maen Mallah, Bijoy Kundu, Loreto Mateu, and Mario Diaz Nava	
93	Chapter in a Book	Using FeFETs as Resistive Synapses in Crossbar-based Analog MAC Accelerating Units	Lei Zhang, David Borggreve, Frank Vanselow, Ralf Brederlow	Intelligent Edge-Embedded Technologies for Digitising Industry
94	Chapter in a Book	Emerging In-memory Computing for Neural Networks	Nellie Laleni, Taha Soliman, Alptekin Vardar, and Thomas Kämpfe	Intelligent Edge-Embedded Technologies for Digitising Industry
95	Chapter in a Book	Artificial Intelligence Advancements for Digitising Industry	Ovidiu Vermesan and Reiner John	Intelligent Edge-Embedded Technologies for Digitising Industry
96	Chapter in a Book	Impact of AI and Digital Twins on IIoT	Bin Han, Björn Richerzhagen, Hans Schotten, Davide Calandra, and Fabrizio Lamberti	
97	Chapter in a Book	Lesson Learnt and Future of AI Applied to Manufacturing	Valerio Frascolla, et al	Intelligent Edge-Embedded Technologies for Digitising Industry

98	Chapter in a Book	Ethical Considerations and Trustworthy Industrial AI Systems	Ovidiu Vermesan, Cristina De Luca, Reiner John, Marcello Coppola, Björn Debaillie, and Giulio Urlini	Intelligent Edge-Embedded Technologies for Digitising Industry
99	Chapter in a Book	Current Challenges of AI Standardisation in the Digitising Industry	Ovidiu Vermesan, Marcello Coppola, Reiner John, Cristina De Luca, Roy Bahr, and Giulio Urlini	Intelligent Edge-Embedded Technologies for Digitising Industry
100	Book/Monograph	Intelligent Edge-Embedded Technologies for Digitising Industry	Editors: Ovidiu Vermesan and Mario Diaz Nava	
101	Chapter in a Book	Benchmarking Neuromorphic Computing for Inference	Simon Narduzzi, Loreto Mateu, Petar Jokic, Erfan Azarkhish, and Andrea Dunbar	Industrial Artificial Intelligence Technologies and Applications
102	Chapter in a Book	Benchmarking the Epiphany Processor as a Reference Neuromorphic Architecture	Maarten Molendijk, Kanishk Vadivel, Federico Corradi, Gert-Jan van Schaik, Amirreza Yousefzadeh, and Henk Corporaal	Industrial Artificial Intelligence Technologies and Applications
103	Chapter in a Book	Temporal Delta Layer: Exploiting Temporal Sparsity in Deep Neural Networks for Time-Series Data	Preetha Vijayan, Amirreza Yousefzadeh, Manolis Sifalakis, and Rene van Leuken	Industrial Artificial Intelligence Technologies and Applications
104	Chapter in a Book	An End-to-End AI-based Automated Process for Semiconductor Device Parameter Extraction	Dinu Purice, Matthias Ludwig, and Claus Lenz	Industrial Artificial Intelligence Technologies and Applications
105	Chapter in a Book	AI Machine Vision System for Wafer Defect Detection	Dmitry Morits, Marcelo Rizzo Piton, and Timo Laakko	Industrial Artificial Intelligence Technologies and Applications
106	Chapter in a Book	Failure Detection in Silicon Package	Saad Al-Baddai and Jan Papadoudis	Industrial Artificial Intelligence Technologies and Applications
107	Chapter in a Book	Feasibility of Wafer Exchange for European Edge AI Pilot Lines	Annika Franziska, et al	Industrial Artificial Intelligence Technologies and Applications
108	Chapter in a Book	Deploying a Convolutional Neural Network on Edge MCU and Neuromorphic Hardware Platforms	Simon Narduzzi, Dorvan Favre, Nuria Pazos Escudero and L. Andrea Dunbar	Industrial Artificial Intelligence Technologies and Applications
109	Chapter in a Book	Efficient Edge Deployment Demonstrated on YOLOv5 and Coral Edge TPU	Ruben Prokscha, Mathias	Industrial Artificial Intelligence Technologies and Applications

			Schneider, and Alfred Höß	
110	Chapter in a Book	Embedded Edge Intelligent Processing for End-To-End Predictive Maintenance in Industrial Applications	Ovidiu Vermesan and Marcello Coppola	Industrial Artificial Intelligence Technologies and Applications
111	Chapter in a Book	AI-Driven Strategies to Implement a Grapevine Downy Mildew Warning System	Luiz Angelo Steffene, Axel Langlet, Lilian Hollard, Lucas Mohimont, Nathalie Gaveau, Marcello Copola, Clément Pierlot, and Marine Rondeau	Industrial Artificial Intelligence Technologies and Applications
112	Book/Monograph	Industrial Artificial Intelligence Technologies and Applications	Editors: Ovidiu Vermesan, Franz Wotawa, Mario Diaz Nava and Björn Debaillie	
113	Book/Monograph	Artificial Intelligence for Digitising Industry	Editors: Ovidiu Vermesan, Reiner John, Cristina De Luca and Marcello Coppola	
114	Chapter in a Book	AI-Powered Collision Avoidance Safety System for Industrial Woodworking Machinery	Conti, F.; Indirli, F.; Latella, A.; Papariello, F.; Puglia, G. M.; Tecce, F.; Urlini, G.; Zanghieri, M.	
115	Article in Journal	A TinyML Platform for On-Device Continual Learning with Quantized Latent Replays	Leonardo Ravaglia; Manuele Rusci; Davide Nadalini; Alessandro Capotondi; Francesco Conti; Luca Benini	IEEE Journal on Emerging and Selected Topics in Circuits and Systems 11.4 (2021)
116	Publication in Conference proceedings/Workshop	State of Charge Estimation using Recurrent Neural Networks with Long Short-Term Memory for Lithium-Ion Batteries	Bockrath, S., Roskopf, A., Koffel, S., Waldhör, S., Srivastava, K., & Lorentz, V. R.	
117	Publication in Conference proceedings/Workshop	foxBMS-free and open BMS platform focused on functional safety and AI	Waldhoer, S., Bockrath, S., Wenger, M., Schwarz, R., & Lorentz, V. R.	PCIM Europe digital days 2020; International Exhibition and Conference for Power Electronics, Intelligent Motion, Renewable Energy and Energy Management

118	Book/Monograph	Embedded Artificial Intelligence: Devices, Embedded Systems, and Industrial Applications	Editors Ovidiu Vermesan, SINTEF, Norway Mario Diaz Nava, STMicroelectronics, France Björn Debaillie, imec, Belgium	
119	Chapter in a Book	Power Optimised Wafermap Classification for Semiconductor Process Monitoring	Ana Pinzari, Thomas Baumela, Liliana Andrade, Marcello Copolla and Frédéric Pétrot	Embedded Artificial Intelligence - Devices, Embedded Systems, and Industrial Applications
120	Chapter in a Book	Generating Trust in Hardware through Physical Inspection	Bernhard Lippmann, Matthias Ludwig and Horst Gieser	Embedded Artificial Intelligence Devices, Embedded Systems, and Industrial Applications
121	Chapter in a Book	Edge AI Platforms for Predictive Maintenance in Industrial Applications	Ovidiu Vermesan and Marcello Copolla	Embedded Artificial Intelligence - Devices, Embedded Systems, and Industrial Applications

7.4.1 AI4DI Books

During the second year of the project, AI4DI partners wrote a book titled **‘Artificial Intelligence for Digitising Industry Applications’** (2022). This book provides in-depth insights into use cases implementing artificial intelligence (AI) applications at the edge. It covers new ideas, concepts, research, and innovation to enable the development and deployment of AI, the industrial internet of things (IIoT), edge computing, and digital twin technologies in industrial environments. The work is based on the research results and activities of the AI4DI (ECSEL JU) project, including an overview of industrial use cases, research, technological innovation, validation, and deployment. This book's sections build on the research, development, and innovative ideas elaborated for applications in five industries: automotive, semiconductor, industrial machinery, food and beverage, and transportation. The articles included under each of these five industrial sectors discuss AI-based methods, techniques, models, algorithms, and supporting technologies, such as IIoT, edge computing, digital twins, collaborative robots, silicon-born AI circuit concepts, neuromorphic architectures, and augmented intelligence, that are anticipating the development of Industry 5.0. Artificial Intelligence for Digitising Industry - Applications.

FIGURE 13 AI4DI BOOK ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE FOR DIGITISING INDUSTRY APPLICATIONS

During the third year of the project, the AI4DI partners issued two more books: „**Intelligent Edge-Embedded Technologies for Digitising Industry**“ (2022) and „**Industrial Artificial Intelligence Technologies and Applications**“ (2022). The two books were released as a result of the aforesaid AI4DI co-organised high level international workshops EAI4IA and EAI in 2022.

The “**Intelligent Edge-Embedded Technologies for Digitising Industry**” book explores new developments, ideas, and concepts in intelligent edge-embedded technologies for the digitising industry. The work is based on recent research results and activities in edge industrial computing, artificial intelligence (AI), the Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT) and digital twin technologies. Each chapter builds on the research, developments and innovative ideas generated by AI4DI, ANDANTE and TEMPO ECSEL JU, as well as other European research projects. Furthermore, the book reviews the core concepts for edge AI advancements in the digitising industry and the impact of AI and digital twins on IIoT. Finally, the book addresses ethical considerations and the trustworthiness of industrial AI systems? core concepts, as well as the current challenges of AI standardisation in the digitising industry.

The book „**Industrial Artificial Intelligence Technologies and Applications**“ offers comprehensive coverage of the topics presented at the ‘International Workshop on Edge Artificial Intelligence for Industrial Applications (EAI4IA)’ in Vienna, on the 25th -26th of July 2022. EAI4IA was co-located with the 31st International Joint Conference on Artificial Intelligence and the 23rd European Conference on Artificial Intelligence (IJCAI-ECAI 2022). It combines the ideas and concepts developed by researchers and practitioners working on providing edge AI methods, techniques, and tools for use in industrial

applications. By highlighting important topics, such as embedded AI for semiconductor manufacturing and trustworthy, dependable, and explainable AI for the digitising industry, verification, validation and benchmarking of AI systems and technologies, AI model development workflows and hardware target platforms deployment, the book explores the challenges faced by AI technologies deployed in various industrial application domains.

FIGURE 14 AI4DI BOOKS: INTELLIGENT EDGE-EMBEDDED TECHNOLOGIES FOR DIGITISING INDUSTRY AND INDUSTRIAL ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE TECHNOLOGIES AND APPLICATIONS

A fourth project book **titled ,Embedded Artificial Intelligence Devices, Embedded Systems, and Industrial Applications ‘** is currently being published as well, taking the total number of project books up to 4:

FIGURE 15 EMBEDDED ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE DEVICES, EMBEDDED SYSTEMS, AND INDUSTRIAL APPLICATIONS

8 Exploitation of the AI4DI foreground

All AI4DI partners have strong interest in participating in this project not only because it fits with their strategic individual plans but also and mainly because they foresee strong potential for the joint exploitation of the project results and the creation of a sustainable collaboration. They all share the vision of cooperating in a win-win manner. The detailed exploitation plans, use cases, and use of the AI4DI foreground are described in the year-end reporting and Confidential deliverables D7.4 ‘Industry-driven AI exploitation studies for different industrial sectors’, D7.5 ‘Industry-driven AI exploitation studies across industrial sectors’, and D7.6 ‘AI based industrial use cases deployment plans for digitising industry’.

Overall, AI4DI partners have each prepared an Exploitation plan for the project results, and reported these plans in confidential Exploitation questionnaires. 40 detailed exploitation questionnaires were filled in by partners, exploitation studies for 26 new products and processes introduced. Two patents were filed.

Due to the Public nature of this deliverable, only non-confidential exploitation outlines are described here, relating to the use of the AI4DI-created foreground.

8.1 Intellectual Property Management

For the success of the project it is essential that all project partners agree on explicit rules concerning intellectual property rights (IPR) ownership, access rights to any Background and Results IP for the execution of the project and the protection of IPR and confidential. Details on these aspects were

agreed upon in the Consortium Agreement. The establishment of intellectual property and other aspects of innovation in this project are primarily done by the respective work packages. Participants jointly or individually prepare patent applications for new concepts and solutions, conceived respectively jointly by one or more participant or solely by one participant. Innovations, concepts and solutions that cannot be protected by patent applications by the participants are made public after agreement between the partners and per the procedure established in the consortium agreement and referred to below, to prevent others to block usage of these results.

Regarding IPR, the use of the European IPR Helpdesk (www.ipr-helpdesk.org) is promoted to help individual participants and partners with questions related to the protection of IPR. A procedure was established to inform all other partners in the project when results of the project will be made public (e.g. in a conference paper), allowing partners to protect IPR before publication. The project maintains a record of all related documents and discussions. This can later be used as a base for resolving conflicts related to IPR filings. Foreground IP shall be owned by the project partner carrying out the work leading to such Foreground IP. If any Foreground IP is created jointly by at least two project partners and it is not possible to distinguish between the contributions of each of the project partners, such work will be jointly owned by the contributing project partners. The same shall apply if, in the course of carrying out work on the project, an invention is made having two or more contributing parties contributing to it, and it is not possible to separate the individual contributions. Such joint inventions and all related patent applications and patents shall be jointly owned by the contributing parties. The full details of the legal framework for the project related to the work, IP-Ownership, Access Rights to Background and Foreground IP for the duration of the project and any other matters of the consortium's interest will be defined in the Consortium Agreement (CA). This was signed by all partners prior to the project start.

9 Conclusion

Dissemination is defined in the Rules for Participation as “public disclosure of the results by any appropriate means (other than resulting from protecting or exploiting the results), including by scientific publications in any medium”³.

To ensure a wide dissemination and communication, and enable successful exploitation of the project results, the AI4DI consortium had created the first draft of the Plan for Use and Dissemination of Foreground, and continued updating this draft throughout the project’s lifetime. According to the plan, a shared visual identity and online presence was created for the project, and a plan for print-based and publication-based dissemination established. The AI4DI project was presented in exhibitions, conferences and workshops, where consortium members actively promoted the project and were involve in networking activities. Besides the activities mentioned above, AI4DI partners are active in many industrial federations, research clusters, and standardization bodies, and actively helped to disseminate the information about the project.

The communication strategy included scientific results, technology advancements and success stories in industrial use cases and therefore addressed the industry, regulatory bodies, the research community and the wider public by organizing dissemination events, workshops, publications and presentations. A mix of channels and means ensured that we reach out to a broad audience and target various interested parties. Communication about the AI4DI project was adapted and tailored to meet the needs of numerous different audiences beyond the project’s own community. Dissemination and exploitation events were also used to not only present specific project results but to represent the project in its entirety.

Overall, AI4DI project was presented in over 60 high-impact events, some of which were co-organised by the consortium partners. Over 100 events in total were attended, where the AI4DI partners discussed the project with key stakeholders. The consortium published four books and 121 publications; it held three webinars, produced newsletters, numerous videos, and a successful social media dissemination with over 1,000 followers/ subscribers. Thousands of project leaflets and brochures were distributed. Project posters were developed for the events and updated for different needs.

Addressing these dissemination channels with different materials, allowed the consortium to fully achieve further exploitation of project results, since every partner of the consortium actively participated in these activities and thus ensure the wide spread of information. Exploitation plans for the consortium are reported in the Confidential deliverable “D7.10 Draft Plan for Use of the Foreground”.

³ European IPR helpdesk for Horizon2020 (<https://www.iprhelpdesk.eu/node/2231>)

10 References

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